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Review Article

PLANT REVIEW ON SOLANUM LYCOPERSICUM (Tomato)¹ Boggula Devika, ² Dr.V. Jayasankar Reddy , ³Dr. K. Venugopal¹Final year B Pharmacy, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati -517506.²M.pharm., Ph.D, Vice Principal and Professor, Department of Pharmacology,
Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati., M.pharm ph D,³Pricipal of Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati.**Abstract:**

Since the majority of tomato varieties in Bangladesh are in hybrid, it is necessary to describe and evaluate morphological variability as a resource for choosing genotype with desirable features in order to generate new varieties. Using development vegetative and fruit features, twenty-two promising tomatoes in bred lines were described twenty-seven morphological trials at the Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI) between October 2009 and march 2010. In the study, 21 quantitative and 6 quantitative physio- morphological features exhibited a broad range of variance, whereas 20 traits shown significant variation among genotypes. There were one or more unique characteristics that might be utilized to identify each genotype. The morphological information for the fruits green shoulder trips, hypocotyl colour; hypocotyl pubescence, leaf type and fruit cross-sectional shape revealed useful diagnostic features that can be utilized to distinguish between the genotypes because they were prevalent in the study. A single morphological characteristic, however makes it challenging to identify every genotype; yet it can improve tomato production diversity and quality. [1,2]

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INTRODUCTION:

NAME OF THE PLANT: Solanum lycopersicum

FAMILY: Solanaceae

A good source of phytochemicals and minerals, including lycopene, potassium, iron, folate, and vitamin C, are tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum*). Tomatoes include phenolic components such flavonoids, hydroxycinnamic acid, chlorogenic acid, homovanillic acid, and ferulic acid in addition to lycopene and vitamin C.

When eaten raw or cooked, tomatoes retain their nutritional value and can contribute significantly to a balanced diet. More than 80 percent of the tomatoes that are farmed commercially are used in processed food like ketchup, soup, and juice. It is well known that eating a lot of tomatoes and tomato-based products has various health benefits, many of which are linked to their antioxidant content. The effects of growing circumstances on tomato cultivars and their health-related characteristics will be covered in this review. [3,4]

SYNONYMS:

Lycopersicon lycopersicum

Lycopersicon esculentum [5]

LOCAL NAMES:

India : Rawangum, Tametokai, Tometo

Australia : Paradeiser

Germany: Tomate, Wid Kirsch

Turkey: Domates

Netherlands: Tomaat [6]

BOTANICAL DESCRIPTION:

The perennial herbaceous plant *solanum lycopersicum* L. is distinguished by its serrated leaves and spreading growth pattern. Usually growing to a height of one to three meters, the plant bears yellow blooms that mature into tomatoes, which are meaty, red or yellow fruits. The pinnate, alternating leaves have hairy surface and noticeable veins. The *solanum* fruit the cultivar of *lycopersicum* L. determines its size, shape and colour; some types Showing fruits that are round, rectangular, or pear-shaped. [7]

GEOGRAPHICAL SOURCE:

The tomato was most likely initially domesticated in Western South America, where the red-fruited *solanum pimpinellifolium*, its likely wild parent, was found. The cherry tomato, *S. lycopersicum* var.

cerasiforme, was most likely the resultant domesticated plant that is ancestors to the contemporary larger-fruited tomato varieties. (8,9) Genomic data, however, indicates that the domestication process might have been more intricate than this. Prior to domestication, *S. Lycopersicon* var. *cerasiforme* might have existed, and features purportedly distinctive of domestication might have been diminished in that variety before being reselected (in an example of convergent evolution) in the cultivated tomato.

According to the investigation, var. *cerasiforme* appeared approximately 78,000 years ago, but the cultivated tomato developed approximately 7,000 years ago (5,000BCE). However, there is a great deal of doubt regarding the potential involvement of humans in this process. (10)

Tomatoes were originally brought to Europe by the Spanish, and Spanish cuisine adopted them. Because it was thought to be poisonous and related to nightshades, it was initially used as an attractive plant elsewhere in Europe. (11)

CULTIVATION:**Climate and soil****1)Temperature and light:**

For a high production and premium quality, tomatoes need a comparatively chilly, dry climates, ranging from temperature to hot and humid tropics. For the majority of types, the ideal temperature range is between 21 and 24C. Although plants can withstand a wide variety of temperatures, they suffer harm from temperature below 10C and above 38C.

Temperature changes affect tomato plant's ability to germinate seeds, grow seedlings, establish flowers and fruit, and produce high quality fruit throughout their life cycle. Pollen production will be minimal if periods of cool or hot weather continue during flowering, fruit formation will be impacted. The plants will die from frost, it is advisable to wait until the winter is unquestionably gone before planting in order to prevent frost damage. Early indoor sowing is an option, fruit colour and leaf colour are all impacted by light intensity. The lowest night time temperature is also significant in tropical low lands. Fruit abortion can occur at temperature lower than 21c.

Table 1: Temperature requirements for different stages of tomato

Stages	Temperature (° C)		
	Min.	Optimum range	Max.
Seed germination	11	16-29	34
Seedling growth	18	21-24	32
Fruit set	18	20-24	30
Red colour development	10	20-24	30

2) Humidity and water:

The sufficiency of local water supplies for tomato cultivation can be ascertained using a straight forward rule of thumb. Tomatoes can be grown in natural environments if there are herbaceous plants present. Rainfall should be expected for at least three months. Fruit may split buds and blossoms will fall off as a result of water stress and extended dry spells. But excessive rain and high humidity will encourage the growth of mold and cause the fruit to spoil. Overcast skies will encourage to mature more slowly, there are nevertheless cultivars that are adaptable. Special tomato varieties for hot-humid conditions are available from seed companies.

3) Soil:

Most mineral soils that are free of salt and have adequate aeration and water-holding capacity are suitable for tomato growth. It favours sandy loam soils that are deep and well-drained. Permeability of the top layer is required a good crop requires a soil depth of 15 to 20cm. Deep ploughing improves root penetration in thick clay soils. Although tomatoes can tolerate a wide range of pH (acidity), they thrive on soils that

have a pH between 5.5 and 6.8 with sufficient fertilizer availability and supply. In general, adding organic matter is favoured for healthy growth. Because of their high water-holding capacity and nutritional deficits, particularly high organic matter soils such as peat soils are less appropriate.

4) Land preparation:

To get the ground ready for a fresh crop, ploughing, also known as digging, is required. IT enhances the structure's ability to hold water. In regions where water is scarce, ploughing also improves water conservation. Follow ploughing enhance the soil's structure and ability to retain water after the previous crop is harvested.

5) Seedlings:

Since growing tomatoes in a nursery yields improved outcomes, tomatoes are typically transplanted. Sowing on a seedbed or a seedling tray-both of which are popular among Southeast Asian farmers-are the two ways that seedling can be raised in nurseries. Plantlets can be adequately preserved, fewer seed quantities are required, the seedling can be chosen for growth and health prior to field planting, and the planting distance is more consistent than after direct field sowing.

6)Transplanting:

Three to six weeks after seeding, move the seedling onto the field. Seedling should be watered less a week prior to transplanting in order to harden them, but they should be watered thoroughly once more 12-14 hours prior to being removed from the seedbed in order to prevent undue root damage. The best seedling for transplanting are those that are 15-25 cm tall and have three to five true leaves. To lessen transplant shock, transplants should be performed in the afternoon or on a gloomy day.

7)Fertilizers and manures:

Tomatoes require fertilization to produce large harvests. Crop nutrients fall into two categories, chemical fertilizers and organic manures.

- Organic manures: There are three forms of organic manures that are compost poultry manure and farmyard manure.
- Chemical fertilizer: This kind of fertilizer is a mixture of nitrogen (N), phosphorous compounds (P₂O₂) and potash.[12]

8)Watering:

There are various types of irrigation to watering the tomato crops:

- Surface irrigation:

The most basic technique involves sprinkling water over flat areas by tiny dykes. Make sure the water dispersed equally.

- Sprinkler irrigation:

In greenhouses, sprinklers with permanent pipes are frequently utilized to keep the paths dry, sprinkler heads are positioned in strips beneath the crops.

9)Harvesting:

Harvesting is depending on the temperature, illness and cultivar sown, harvesting will be last for around one month. There are four stages to harvest the tomatoes. That are;

Stage 1: When the tomato is sliced, the seeds are white and cuttable.

Stage 2: The seeds are ripe and brown with some juice.

Stage 3: When chopped the seeds are thrown aside and the interior part remains green.

Stage 4: The colour of the juice is red

Harvesting tomatoes at the early stage of maturity will result in tomatoes of low quality.[13]

COLLECTION:

The tomatoes which are produced on 3.7 million hectares and produces around 100 million tons of fresh fruit annually. It is the second most important vegetable crop in the world after potatoes. Because so much fruit is consumed, tomatoes play a significant

role in human diets. In addition to being consumed fresh, the fruit is also processed and used in soups, purees and canned goods. The tomato can give carotenoid and flavonoid pigments that give the fruit its range of yellow, red and orange. [14, 15]

A lengthy history of study has helped to identify the parts of tomato genome that regulate a variety of significant features such as disease resistance, yield and fruit quality. The first tomato genome was sequenced 10 years ago. Tomatoes are a great model plant for studying dicot agricultural species, particularly those with luscious fruits because of their diploid nature, genetic resources and variety of single gene mutants.[16]

We have compiled a selection of papers in this unique collection to examine the most recent advancements and scientific discoveries in tomato molecular biology. The main points of the studies together place the scientific finding in the framework of plant growth. Among other things, plant design affects the quantity of reproductive shoots which is a crucial element in determining agricultural output. Although research on the hormonal regulation of plant architecture has been going on for more than a century.[17]

New developments in genomics have sped up our comprehension of the molecular underpinnings of this process. The tomato is a particularly helpful model for examining the relationship between plant architectural characteristics. In tomatoes, side branching is undesired and leads to unnecessary labour and management expenses. [18]

MORPHOLOGY:

Plant growth type, size, stem pubescence density, foliage density, degree of leaf dissection, leaf shape(Figure1),corolla colour, style shape, style position, external colour of immature fruit, presence of green trips in the fruit, fruit pubescence, predominant fruit shape (figures2,3),external colour of mature fruit, shoulder shape, cross-sectional shape, and blossom end with the use of the colour chart in the IBPGR description list for *S. lycopersicum*, shapes were simply identified using the visual technique. In order to identify the key characteristics required for plant breeding that would eventually support sustainable development in Nigeria, West Africa, and other African locations, morphological characterisation was carried out for the four types. The table displays the measured parameters as well as IBPGR descriptor keys. [19]

In order to evaluate the potential relationship between qualitative and quantitative morphological features and accessions, multivariate statistical analyses were conducted in this study. SPSS (version 20.0) and PAST (Paleontological Statistics, version 1.34), were used to evaluate the gathered data. To assess the importance of the variations between the accessions, analysis of variance was performed for both qualitative and quantitative morphological characteristics. To ascertain the degree of genetic variation and the proportion of similarities within and between the accession, principal component analysis (PCA) and paired Group Cluster Analysis (PGCA) were employed. [20]

This study used multivariate statistical analysis to evaluate the potential correlation between quantitative and qualitative physical traits and advancements. SPSS (version 20.0) and PAST (Paleontological Statistics, version 1.34) were used to evaluate the data that was gathered. For both qualitative and quantitative morphological characteristics, analysis of variance was performed in order to ascertain the significance of the variations between the accessions. Utilizing Principal Component Analysis (PCA), and Paired Group Cluster Analysis (PGCA), the proportion of similarities among the accessions and the degree of genetic variation were ascertained. [21, 22]

MICROSCOPY:

Microscopy can reveal many details about its structure and composition.

- Skin: A barrier of tightly packed cells that protects the tomato from pests, dehydration and disease.
- Flesh: Also known as the mesocarp, this juicy part stores nutrients and water.
- Seeds: Each seed has the potential to grow into a new tomato plant.

- Cell structure: The size, shape and arrangement of cells in a tomato's tissues vary depending on the ripening stage.
- Cell wall thickness: The thickness of cell walls varies by tissue type and ripeness.
- Chloroplasts: Transmission of electron microscopy can reveal the structure of chloroplasts in a tomato's fruit pericarp. [23, 24]

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS:

Solanum lycopersicum L. has a diverse array of bioactive substances, including as vitamins, minerals, antioxidants, and phytochemicals, in its chemical composition. Particularly abundant in carotenoids are tomatoes, which include beta-carotene, lutein, and

lycopene, which support their rich hue and antioxidant qualities. Moreover, vitamins C and vitamin K are found in considerable concentrations in tomatoes. Potassium and folate which makes them an important source of vital minerals. [25]

TRADITIONAL USES:

Around the world, traditional medical systems have used *solanum lycopersicum L.* for a variety of therapeutic objectives. Indigenous cultures are frequently included in tomatoes into cures for condition like digestive illnesses, skin issues, and inflammation. Furthermore, topical tomato extract treatments were thought to assist the healing of wounds and reduce sunburn. Although contemporary some of these have been scientifically validated by research customary application. [26]

- **Culinary purposes:**

Tomatoes are a staple in many international culinary traditions. They are an essential component of many different cuisines, including salads, soups, and sauces. Tomatoes are a staple in many traditional Mexican, Indian, Mediterranean, and Italian foods. [27]

- **Medicinal applications:**

Tomatoes have been utilized for their therapeutic qualities in traditional medical systems such as Ayurveda and Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM). They are utilized because they are thought to have cooling qualities. Can relieve ailments such as urinary tract troubles, digestive disorders, and inflammation. [28]

- **Skin care:**

Tomatoes have been employed in skincare practices in some civilizations. For instance, because of its acidic and antioxidant qualities, tomato pulp or juice is applied topically in some Asian countries to enhance complexion, lessen acne, and lighten imperfections. [29]

- **Eye Health:**

According to local traditional knowledge, eating tomatoes may help maintain eye health. It is thought that tomatoes' high level of vitamin C, lycopene, and

other antioxidants shield the eyes from oxidative damage and promote eye health. [30]

- **Home Remedies:**

As was previously noted, tomatoes are frequently used in traditional home remedies for a number of reasons, including sunburn relief, skin irritation relief, and skin health promotion. These treatments are firmly anchored in cultural customs and frequently transmitted across the generations. [31]

- **Symbolism and Rituals:**

Tomatoes are used in rituals and ceremonies or have symbolic meaning in certain cultures. They might be utilized in religious rites or harvest festival rituals, or they could represent fertility and wealth. [32]

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY:

- **Anti-inflammatory:**

Bioactive chemicals found in tomatoes have anti-inflammatory qualities that may help reduce inflammation related illnesses like asthma and arthritis. Tomato extracts have demonstrated promise as possible anti-inflammatory drugs in preclinical research by modifying inflammatory pathways and cytokine production. [33]

- **Neuroprotective Effects:**

Numerous compounds found in tomatoes have been studies for possible neuroprotective effects. Antioxidant-active compounds including lycopene, vitamin C, and flavonoids may help shield neurons from oxidative damage and lower the incidence of neurodegenerative illnesses like Parkinson's and Alzheimer's. [34]

- **Anti-diabetic activity:**

According to preliminary research polyphenols, and flavonoids, two parts of *solanum lycopersicum L.* may have anti-diabetic effects. These substances may lessen difficulties related to diabetes, control blood glucose levels, and enhance insulin sensitivity. [35]

- **Anti-microbial Activity:**

Solanum lycopersicum L. has a number of bioactive chemicals that have shown antibacterial efficacy against a range of pathogens, including viruses, fungi, and bacteria. These substances may aid in the prevention and treatment of infections disorders by preventing the growth of dangerous germs. [36]

- **Antioxidant properties:**

The main pigment in tomatoes, lycopene, has strong antioxidant properties that scavenge free radicals and lessen oxidative stress. Lycopene has been shown in numerous studies to play a part in shielding cells from reactive oxygen species-induced damage, which may lower the risk of chronic illnesses like cancer and cardiovascular disease. [37]

- **Cardioprotective Effect:**

Due in part to their high lycopene content and other elements that are good for the heart, eating tomatoes has been linked to cardiovascular health advantages. By lowering blood pressure, cholesterol, and platelet aggregation, lycopene may help minimize the risk of heart disease and stroke. [38]

- **Anticancer Activity:**

Tomato consumption and the incidence of some malignancies, especially prostate cancer, may be inversely correlated, according to several epidemiological research. The potential anticancer effects of lycopene and other bioactive chemicals found in tomatoes, including as their antioxidant, anti-proliferative, and apoptotic qualities, have been studied. [39]

- **Gastrointestinal Health Benefits:**

Tomatoes have the potential to improve gastrointestinal health since they are high in vitamins, minerals, and dietary fibre. Eating tomatoes and products made from them has been linked to better digestion, regular bowel movements, and a lower risk of diseases such colorectal cancer and constipation. [40]

- **Skin Health Promotion:**

According to some research, using tomato extract topically or consuming them inside may improve the health of the skin. Antioxidant-rich ingredients like lycopene and vitamin C can help shield the skin from UV-induced damage, encourage collagen synthesis, and enhance the texture and appearance of the skin overall.

CONCLUSION:

The tomato plant, *Solanum Lycopersicon* L., is a widely grown crop valued for its Savory and nutrient-dense fruits as well as a storehouse of pharmacologically active chemicals with potential health benefits. A through analysis of *solanum lycopersicum* L.'S pharmacognosy and

pharmacological activity has been conducted in this paper, covering its botanical description, chemical components, traditional usage, and contemporary pharmacological applications. The botanical traits and chemical makeup of tomatoes have been clarified through pharmacogenetic research, while pharmacological studies have illuminated their various biological activities, such as their anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, cardioprotective, and anticancer qualities. Even through we now know a lot more about the health advantages of *solanum lycopersicum* L., further research is still required to fully explore its medicinal potential.

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